

CURING OF COMPOSITE PREPREG LAMINATES BY RESISTANCE HEATING OF INTERNAL CARBON VEILS

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SUMMARY: The goal of this investigation is to assess the feasibility of using internal carbon fiber resistance heaters with temperature feedback to cure laminated composites comprised of either S2 glass or IM7 carbon fiber reinforced epoxy prepreg. Internal temperature distributions and cumulative energy consumptions were measured in unidirectional laminates with 6.4 mm (50 ply) and 38.1 mm (300 ply) thicknesses. The temperature distributions revealed a lack of deviations in temperature from the manufacturer's recommended cure cycles commonly seen in thick laminates cured by conventional means, although a means of improving temperature uniformity is needed. Volumetric energy usage was five to ten times greater in the thin laminates than in the thick laminates cured with internal heaters. This difference was attributed to incomplete curing in certain areas and a higher volume to surface ratio in the latter.

KEYWORDS: processing, thick laminates, internal heating, resistance heating

INTRODUCTION

During the cure process of fiber reinforced epoxy laminates, a phenomenon known as temperature overshoot or spiking has been known to occur. Temperature overshoot occurs when the thickness and thermal diffusivity of a volume of material are such that the heat generated by the exothermic curing process cannot be transferred to the external surfaces of the material at a rate which will prevent the interior of the material from reaching dangerously high temperatures. Scott and Beck [1] measured temperature overshoots in 128-, 64-, and 32-ply carbon/epoxy laminates processed in an autoclave. In the 128-ply carbon/epoxy laminate, the maximum temperature overshoot was 60°C. Kenny [2] observed 30°C temperature overshoots in an 8-mm-thick carbon/epoxy laminate cured in a standard autoclave process. Butler and Engel [3] observed a 70°C overshoot due to the exotherm of 50-cm-thick glass/epoxy composites made by resin transfer molding. Overshoot temperatures of these magnitudes could possibly cause thermal damage in certain epoxy resin composites.

In terms of the potential for temperature overshoot, Kenny et al. [4] defined a thick composite based on material properties. The idea of a half thickness, h_{AD} , of the material was introduced, where the total thickness of a part would be twice its half thickness. Equation 1 is the expression for h_{AD} ,

$$h_{AD} = \{k / [\rho C_p K_0 \exp(Q / RT_c)]\}^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where k is the composite thermal conductivity, ρ is the composite density, C_p is the specific heat of the composite, K_0 is a frequency factor used in describing the kinetic rate constant derived from a thermokinetic model for nonautocatalytic reactions, Q is the activation energy for cure of the resin, R is the universal gas constant, and T_c is the processing temperature. The half thickness reported by Kenny [2, 4] for carbon epoxy prepregs is approximately 1 cm. It is indicated in Eqn 1 that materials with higher thermal conductivity and processing temperature and lower density, specific heat, frequency factor, and cure activation energy will have a greater half thickness and therefore less tendency for temperature spiking for a given thickness of material. Since composites composed of glass or carbon fiber are differentiated in these terms by higher thermal conductivity, lower density, and lower specific heat in the carbon composite, it can be expected that carbon composites are less likely than glass composites to undergo temperature spikes during cure — all else being the same.

There have been methods developed for dealing with temperature spiking due to the exothermic reaction in fiber reinforced epoxy composites. Among these are the manufacturer's thick part processing cycle, continuous curing or simultaneous lay-up and *in-situ* cure process [5], staged curing [6], and embedded resistance heating [3].

The objective of this investigation is to evaluate the internal heating method developed by Butler and Engel [3] for resin transfer molding applications as it applies to carbon and glass reinforced epoxy laminates of thicknesses of 6.4 and 38.1 mm. New contributions of the present work include the following: the incorporation of a single-zone, internal temperature feedback loop; the calculation of real-time power and cumulative energy used during the cure cycle; the application of the method to prepreg material systems; the comparison of two material systems with identical resin types and resin volume fractions but different fiber types; and the comparison of thin and moderately thick parts. Thermocouples were embedded at various locations through the thickness of the laminates and monitored continuously. Temperature distributions in laminates cured by two different methods — computer controlled hot press curing and internal resistance heating element curing — were compared.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The material systems used in the present investigation were Hercules MAGNAMITE[®] carbon prepreg tape IM7/8551-7A and Hercules MAGNAMITE[®] S2-glass[®] prepreg tape S2/8551-7A. These zero-bleed prepregs were chosen due to their availability and also due to their having the same volume fraction and type of resin, thereby allowing a controlled comparison of the effect of fiber type on curing characteristics. The laminates used were nominally either 50- or 300- plies thick. The manufacturer's cured ply thickness were 0.140 mm for the carbon prepreg and 0.127 mm for the glass prepreg. Hence, the nominal thicknesses of the thin and thick laminates were assumed to be 6.4 and 38.1 mm, respectively. As will be described below, all laminates were essentially unidirectionally reinforced. Two layers of 102 by 76 mm carbon veil with randomly oriented chopped fibers were used for each internal resistance heater, also called the heating patch. A single veil had an average areal density of 16 g/m². Copper wires which had 76 mm of insulation stripped at the end were placed across opposite ends of the veil so that current passed along the 102 mm dimension. The two wires thus sandwiched between two veils comprised a heating patch. The thin laminates used one heating patch at the mid-plane location and the thick laminates used three heating patches connected in series as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: An exploded view of the internal resistance heating setup for a 300 ply, 38-mm glass/epoxy laminate

In order to determine the resistance and, hence, power dissipation of the patches throughout the cure cycle, a dummy carbon patch was used in a separate DC voltage divider circuit. A low (0.5 - 1 V) DC voltage source introduced current to the circuit while an 8 Ω ceramic resistor was used as the ballast resistor across which voltage was recorded (Fig. 1). A 220 μF capacitor was placed in parallel with the ballast resistor to eliminate electrical noise that resulted from the proximity of the relatively high AC voltage heating patches to the low DC voltage dummy patch. The dummy patches were located 7 and 15 plies from the middle surface of the thin and thick laminates, respectively. If the ballast resistor voltage is V_b , the DC source voltage is V_s , and the ballast resistance is R_b , then the dummy patch resistance, R_p , is given by Eqn 2.

$$R_p = R_b(V_s / V_b - 1) \quad (2)$$

The *average* power dissipated by the series-connected patches, P , was calculated using Eqn 3,

$$P = (V_{AC})^2 / 2R_H \quad (3)$$

where V_{AC} is the *peak* voltage output of the AC source and R_H is the sum of the resistances of all the heating patches in the specimen. At any time during the cure cycle, each heating patch was assumed to have a resistance equal to that continuously measured with the *in-situ* dummy patch, thereby accounting for, in an approximate sense, the effects of contact pressure between patches and wires, liquid epoxy infusion, degree of cure, and process temperature on

patch resistance. To ascertain the internal temperature distribution, at least one type J thermocouple was inserted near the center of all four patches in the case of the thick laminates (Fig. 1) and at four comparable locations (scaled for the number of plies) in the thin laminates.

To manufacture the thick laminates, a rectangular aluminum mold was fabricated with inner dimensions of 127 by 102 mm by up to 76 mm thick. A variable thickness, 127 by 102 mm caul plate was manufactured to fit snugly into the mold and was used to transfer compaction pressure from press platens to the laminates. Near the center of one of the 127 mm sides of the mold, several small holes were made to allow passage of thermocouple and electrical wires. The thin laminates were manufactured using a pair of 330 by 304 by 13 mm aluminum caul plates with putty material used to confine the planar dimensions of the prepreg to 127 by 102 mm. The laminates were made with all their fibers oriented in the 102 mm direction, except for the carbon/epoxy laminates which were cured by internal patch resistance heating. In these exceptions, a $[0/90]_s$ laminate of glass/epoxy prepreg was added above and below each carbon patch to prevent an electrical short circuit with the surrounding carbon prepreg material. To account for the added thickness of the glass/epoxy insulation, eight plies of carbon epoxy prepreg were subtracted for each carbon patch present in the thick carbon specimen. No such correction was made in the thin carbon specimen, resulting in added thickness in comparison with the thin glass specimen. Attempts were made to minimize heat loss from the molds to the surrounding environment when using internal patch resistance heating by wrapping glass wool insulation around the sides of the molds and by placing 13-mm-thick plywood sheets between the mold and the upper and lower platens of the press.

Two curing methods were investigated: hot press curing and internal carbon patch curing. The hot press was a Tetrahedron model MTP-14 with 35.6 cm square platens and computer controlled force and temperature. The internal patch curing was done with a 120 VAC (peak), 10 A (peak) variable autotransformer as the power source and the MTP-14 for compaction force only. An on/off type temperature controller was used to control the temperature as measured by a separate thermocouple placed on the center-most heating patch (Fig. 1).

During a typical experiment, a stopwatch and analog voltmeter were used to manually record, every few minutes, the peak voltage output of the AC source for the heater patches. Power source peak voltages for the thin and thick laminates were held constant at values of approximately 25 and 40 VAC, respectively, throughout an experiment. Time, thermocouple readings, the DC dummy source voltage and DC dummy ballast resistor voltage were all recorded every 50 sec with a computer. Elapsed time that the AC power was applied to the heating patches was measured against real time by periodically recording the time from an analogue clock powered by the same on/off temperature controller which energized the power patches. Hence, based on Eqn 3, the cumulative energy dissipated in the specimen, E , was determined by multiplying the averaged average power during each interval, P_i , by the respective clock time increment during that interval, Δt_i , and summing as in Eqn 4.

$$E = \sum_i P_i(\Delta t_i) \quad (4)$$

RESULTS

Temperature profiles for a hot-press cured 38.1-mm-thick glass/epoxy laminate shown in Fig. 2 reveal some inaccuracy in the tracking of the temperature versus the MRC cycle, particularly during temperature ramps. The two middle thermocouples in this experiment were located at the middle and at the quarter point along the length of the laminate. One of these recorded the maximum temperature spike of 10°C after the beginning of the 177°C dwell. The deviations from the MRC were even less in the 38.1-mm-thick carbon/epoxy laminate and in thinner laminates of either type cured in the hot press (data not shown here). These data suggest that the materials tested here, in conjunction with the high thermal conductivity mold and good thermal coupling between the mold and temperature-controlled platens of the hot press, do not develop dangerous temperature spikes during the standard cure process. Based on visual inspection, these specimens appeared to be well-consolidated and fully-cured.

Fig. 2: Temperature profiles in a 38.1-mm glass/epoxy laminate cured in a hot press

Representative dummy patch resistance data from two internally heated 6.4-mm laminates shown in Fig. 3 indicate a decrease from approximately 3 to 2 Ω shortly after the application of consolidation pressure. Dummy patch resistance data for the 38.1-mm laminates were essentially identical to those shown in Fig. 2. The 33% drop in resistance attributed to contact pressure is important from the standpoint of the power dissipation calculation (Eqn 3) as well as the physical interpretation that liquid epoxy infusion, temperature change and degree of cure did not significantly affect patch resistance in these experiments.

Temperature profiles in the 6.4-mm internally-heated glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy laminates are shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. Temperature ramps were rather course due the manual stepwise increase in settings of the temperature controller, but neither specimen exhibited any significant temperature overshoot. In both figures, the middle thermocouple did not measure exactly the same temperature as the nearby but separate controller thermocouple

which was also located at the midplane of the specimen. These variations of up to 15°C could be due to variations in power input across the plane of the middle heating patches, possibly related to the visually apparent density variations in the patch material from point to point.

Fig. 3: Dummy carbon patch resistance during the cure cycle

Fig. 4: Temperature profiles in a 6.4-mm glass/epoxy laminate with one heating patch

The instantaneous average power dissipated by the single heating patch of a 6.4-mm carbon/epoxy specimen is shown in Fig. 6 to vary from 90 W at the outset to 160 W during the final dwell due to the decrease in resistance of the heating patch shown in Fig. 3. The integrated value of cumulative average energy is also shown in Fig. 6, but it should be kept in mind that this value is arrived at not by integration of average power along the real time axis but, rather, along the actual heating time axis (the time the heating patch is energized), which is not shown in Fig. 6. Average power dissipation while the internal heater was energized in the 6.4-mm glass/epoxy specimen was approximately 170 W.

Fig. 5: Temperature profiles in a 6.4-mm carbon/epoxy laminate with one heating patch

Fig. 6: Average power in a 6.4-mm carbon/epoxy specimen with one heating patch

The temperature profiles of 38.1-mm specimens indicated spatial temperature deviations of up to 60°C from the MRC cycle, mainly in the top and bottom regions of the material (Figs. 7 and 8). However, no evidence of temperature spiking was seen in any region. It is apparent that relatively more power needs to be put into the thicker materials near the extreme top and bottom of the laminates to overcome their natural tendency to become hotter near the midplane during cure. Based on visual inspection, it was observed that the 38.1-mm laminates did not fully cure near the outer extreme positions in the mold due to the cooler temperature there.

Fig. 7: Temperature profiles in a 38.1-mm glass/epoxy laminate with three heating patches

The average power dissipation of the three internal heaters when energized in either 38.1-mm specimen was approximately 150 W. The cumulative average energy dissipations of the 38.1-mm specimens are compared to those of the 6.4-mm specimens in Table 1. Cumulative energies of the 38.1-mm specimens are similar to each other and five to ten times less than those of the thinner specimens, regardless of material type. The results therefore do not indicate a strong link between fiber type and energy required to cure. There is, however, a strong indication that thinner laminates take more energy per unit volume to cure than do thick laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation of 6.4- and 38.1-mm-thick laminates composed of glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy prepreg, minor temperature undershoots and overshoots were recorded in specimens cured in a hot press according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle, particularly in the thickest glass/epoxy laminate. These results suggested that material type and thickness play a role in the ability to control temperature uniformly in a hot press.

Resistance of the carbon veil (patch) material used to promote curing by internally heating the laminates while compaction pressure was applied by a press dropped by approximately 33% due to the application of pressure. No other factors such as resin infusion, temperature change, or degree of cure affected patch resistance. Variations of up to 15°C in temperature across the plane of a typical carbon patch during cure were attributed to areal nonuniformities of patch composition.

Typical values of average power dissipated in all specimens when the internal heaters were energized were between 150 and 170 W. This amount of power was unable to fully cure the 38.1-mm glass/epoxy laminate in certain regions, but all other specimens appeared to be fully cured and well consolidated. Cumulative energies used were somewhat lower in the thicker specimens (240-320 W·hr) than in the thinner specimens (410-470 W·hr). The energy per unit volume applied to the thin specimens was 5-10 times that applied to the thick specimens, which may be related to the higher surface-to-volume ratio of the thin specimens and the higher resulting heat loss to the environment. However, the differing thermal characteristics of the carbon and glass fibers did not correlate with significantly different energy consumptions per unit volume of material. No temperature spikes were observed in the internally-heated specimens, although it is clear that more energy needs to be applied near the exterior regions of thicker specimens due to their tendency to become hottest in the interior regions during cure.

Fig. 8: Temperature profiles in a 38.1-mm carbon/epoxy laminate with three heating patches

Table 1: Dimensions and energy values for carbon/epoxy (c) and glass/epoxy (g) specimens

Specimen	No. Plies	Actual Thickness (mm)	Volume (cm ³)	Energy (W·hr)	Energy/Volume (W·hr/mm ³)
6.4-mm c	66	8.4	108.2	410	3.8
6.4-mm g	50	6.1	78.7	470	6.0
38.1-mm c	300	35.6	458.8	320	0.70
38.1-mm g	300	35.6	458.8	240	0.52

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